

BIBLIOMETRIK ANALIZ: CHEK2 GENI VA KO'KRAK BEZI SARATONI

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Saraton hastaligi butun dunyoda sog'liqni saqlash tashkilotlarining asosiy muammolaridan biri bo'lib kelmoqda. Hayot davomida saraton (75 yoshgacha) rivojlanish xavfi taxminan 20% va saraton kasalligidan o'lish xavfi 10% tashkil qiladi [1]. Har besh kishidan biri hayoti davomida saraton kasalligiga duchor bo'ladi va hastalikga chalingan bemorlarning o'ntasidan bittasi kasallikdan vafot etadi. 2020-yilda saraton bilan kasallanishning 2,26 million yangi holatlar qayt etilgan [2]. Ayollarda ko'krak bezi saratonini dunyo bo'ylab eng ko'p tashxis qo'yiladigan va hastalangan ayollar o'limiga sabab bo'ladigan saraton turi hisoblanadi [3].

Ko'krak bezi saratonining ro'y berayotgan tendentsiyasi o'zgarmasa, faqat aholi sonining o'sishi va qarishi natijasida 2040 yilga borib 3 milliondan ortiq yangi kassalanish holatlari va 1 million o'lim holati qayit etiladi deb taxmin qilinmoqda . Bugungi kunga kelib, ko'krak bezi saratonini rivojlanish xavfi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan turli darajadagi penetrant mutatsiyalar, shu jumladan CHEK2 genidagi mutatsiyalar (tekshirish nuqtasi kinaza geni) ma'lum [4].

CHEK2 geni bir necha populyasiyalarda KBSga moyil bo'lgan gen ekanligi aniqlandi. 2002 yilda CHEK2 genidagi mutasiya KBS ni kelib chiqishiga sabab bo'lishi xaqida ma'lum qilindi va keyingi olib borilgan ko'pkina tadqiqotlar buni tasdiqladi [5-7].

Ishning maqsadi: 2018-2022 yillarda ko'krak bezi saratonini va CHEK2 geni o'rtasida bog'liqligi haqida chop etilgan maqolalarning bibliometrik tahlili.

Materiallar va metodlar: CHEK 2 geni mutatsiyalari haqida keltirilgan eng ko'p iqtibos olgan maqolalar Scopus maqolalar bazasidan olindi. Maqolalar soni 550tani tashkil etdi. Olingan natijalar VOS viewer va boshqa onlayin bibliometrik analiz platformalaridan foydalanib analiz, grafik taxlillar qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: CHEK 2 geni, ko'krak bezi saratonini, mutatsiya.

Olingan natijalar: maqolalar chop etilishining soni asosan 2018-2019 va 2020-2021 yillarda o'sish ko'zatilgan. Ilmiy izlanishlar, maqolalarning chop etilishi, asosan AQSh ilmiy tekshirish institutlarida olib borilganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin [8]. Buyuk Britaniya va Kanada keyingi o'rinlarni egalamoqda. Bu holatni iqtisodi rivojlangan davlatlar ilmiy izlanishlarga ko'p mablag' ajrata olish imkoniga ega ekanligi bilan bog'ladik [9]. Mavzuimizni fan sohasi bilan bog'laganimizda ilmiy izlanishlar asosan (49%) meditsina sohasi bilan bo'gliqligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Bu holatni biz o'rganilayotgan mavzuimiz inson salomatligi bilan uzviy bog'langanligi sababli deb xulosa qildik. Mavzu bo'yicha eng ko'p maqolalar “Redox Biology” jurnalida chop etilganligini ko'rish mumkin [10-13]. Shuni ham ta'kidlab o'tish kerakki, jurnal IF va maqolalarga berilgan iqtiboslar soni o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik unchalik muhim ahamiyatga ega emas .

Xulosa: So'ngi izlanishlar shuni ko'rsatadiki CHEK 2 geni saratonning nasliy kelib chiqish turlarining rivojlanishida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bu mavzu bo'yicha olib borilayotgan tekshiruvlar yil sayin ortib bormoqda. CHEK 2 genidagi mutatsiyalarni o'rganish nafaqat to'g'ri tashxis qo'yish balki bemorlarda davo usullarini to'g'ri tanlashda ham muhim ahamiyatga ega.

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